

1 **Predictive model for sustainable exploitation of geothermal resources**
2 **in Africa: The case of Olkaria geothermal field**

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7 **Abstract**

8 Geothermal energy represents a crucial resource for a sustainable future, particularly in Africa's Rift
9 Valley, which holds significant untapped potential. Despite this, high upfront costs and development
10 risks remain major barriers. This study introduces a simplified model calibrated with real data from
11 the Olkaria geothermal field in Kenya. The model enables rapid preliminary assessments of both
12 technical and economic performance, requiring only minimal input data. Additionally, it incorporates
13 a Life Cycle Assessment to evaluate environmental impacts, an aspect rarely explored in African
14 geothermal studies. The research analyses various technological configurations, including Single
15 Flash, Double Flash, and Organic Rankine Cycle systems, aiming to improve efficiency without
16 additional drilling. Findings show that integrating a binary ORC with existing flash systems can boost
17 energy output by up to 20.1%, with only a modest rise in the Levelized Cost of Electricity . Compared
18 to the current Olkaria IV setup, hybrid systems demonstrated lower carbon emissions and reduced
19 material resource use. The results confirm that ORC integration offers the most sustainable pathway
20 for developing high-temperature geothermal resources in the East African Rift. This approach
21 balances energy efficiency, economic feasibility, and environmental impact, providing valuable
22 guidance for future power plant development in regulatory-constrained settings.

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35 **Keywords:** Geothermal energy, Kenya, African development, Renewable Energy, Sustainability
36 power plant

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38 1 Introduction

39 Geothermal energy is considered one of the prospective alternatives for displacing baseload power
40 supplied by fossil fuels to partly offset energy-related greenhouse gas emissions [Sharmin et al.,
41 2023]. The African continent, where energy demand is projected to increase tremendously in the next
42 30 years, has vast geothermal resources, mainly located along the African Rift System [Omenda,
43 2015]. However, the high risk associated with the upstream development and the attendant high costs
44 still prove a challenge to tapping into these resources [Shortall et al., 2015]. So far, out of the 15 GW
45 potential in the African Rift System, about 1.02 GW has been developed, with 95% of this developed
46 in Kenya [Omenda et al., 2025]. Surface exploration and exploration drilling to prove geothermal
47 resources are expensive and attract less interest from financiers. Thus, efforts are being put in place
48 by the global geothermal community to develop tools to help conduct preliminary exploration
49 assessments remotely to assess the techno-economic feasibility and boost investor confidence in
50 geothermal projects.

51 Previously, researchers have developed software tools for evaluating the techno-economic feasibility
52 of geothermal projects, considering factors such as resource assessment, plant design, financial
53 modelling, and market dynamics. GETEM is an Excel-based tool used to estimate the Levelized Cost
54 of Electricity (LCOE) for geothermal projects, including hydrothermal and Enhanced Geothermal
55 System (EGS). It allows users to input technical and economic parameters and uses a discounted cash
56 flow method to calculate costs and assess different scenarios [Mine, 2016]. GEOPHIRES is a flexible
57 and user-friendly tool for evaluating geothermal systems' technical and economic performance,
58 including electricity generation, direct heat use, and combined heat and power (CHP). It simulates all
59 major system components—reservoir, wells, surface plant—and calculates key metrics like LCOE
60 and LCOH using user inputs or default correlations [Beckers and McCabe, 2019]. FGEM is designed
61 to assess flexible geothermal operations' technical and economic feasibility by modeling the
62 interaction between the subsurface, surface plant, and energy markets. It supports the evaluation of
63 different dispatch strategies, including mass flow variation, wellhead pressure modulation, and
64 integration with thermal energy storage (TES) and lithium-ion batteries (LiBs) [Aljubran and Horne,
65 2024].

66 While these tools provide detailed and thorough analyses, they are mainly useful in later stages after
67 a data collection campaign, because they need a large amount of input data. This includes information
68 about the subsurface, the well, the power plant, and sometimes economic or environmental factors.
69 Collecting this data can be difficult, particularly in areas with limited data availability as witnessed
70 with most of the geothermal areas in Africa. Thus, the question remains whether it is possible to
71 predict the techno-economic performance of a plant with limited available data. This approach could
72 be valuable for assessing geothermal potential on a large scale. Moreover, a significant gap in
73 literature is the inability of these methods to evaluate the potential cascade exploitation of the
74 resource, an issue that remains insufficiently addressed.

75 Another important aspect is including environmental factors to provide a more complete and holistic
76 analysis. In the literature, the life cycle assessment (LCA) methodology is commonly employed to
77 evaluate the environmental impacts of geothermal plants [Parisi et al., 2020; GECO, 2023; Zuffi et
78 al., 2020]. However, despite its widespread use, analyses in the African context remain conspicuously
79 absent [Mukoro et al., 2021].

80 Therefore, as part of the collaborations established within the European project LEAP-RE [LEAP-
81 RE 2020], a simplified model has been developed to assess the feasibility of geothermal resource
82 utilization for electricity generation using a minimal set of input parameters. The model is structured
83 in a modular framework, allowing for the evaluation of different technologies individually, as well
84 as their potential integration. This enables a cascading utilization approach, where higher-temperature

85 resources are used first, followed by lower-temperature ones, or the enhancement of existing
86 geothermal plants. The model is simulated using data from Kenya's Olkaria geothermal field, which
87 is in the axial of the central Kenyan Rift. Currently, the Olkaria geothermal field is the second most
88 productive worldwide, surpassed only by the geysers in the USA [Renkens, 2019]. To support the
89 analysis a data collection effort was conducted to perform the first LCA of the a geothermal plant in
90 Africa, addressing a gap in the existing literature [Mukoro et al., 2021]. Finally, the results of the
91 techno-economic and environmental assessments are integrated to provide a decision-making
92 framework for evaluating the sustainability of the proposed solutions.

93 **2 Methodology**

94 **2.1 General Approach**

95 To characterize a geothermal resource, several parameters are required [Barbier, 2002; Reed and
96 Anderson, 2011; Di Pippo, 2008]. However, four key parameters are selected in the context of
97 developing a simplified predictive techno-economic model. These parameters are fundamental for
98 calculations and are as follows:

- 99 • *Reservoir Temperature* ($T_{\text{geo,in}}$). It defines the possible applications (electricity
100 production/heat/cold) and also the potential of the selected technology;
- 101 • *Mass flow rate* (m_{geo}). It defines the capacity of the energy systems and their components,
102 such as heat exchangers, turbines, and other mechanical components;
- 103 • *Well Depth* (L_{well}). It defines the depth of the well and thus results in a possible change in
104 temperature at the wellhead and thus at the input to an energy system;
- 105 • *Ambient air temperature* (T_{air}). It defines the average temperature of the environment and the
106 related interactions at the condenser and cooling tower of power plants;

107 The predictive model, presented in this work, is divided into two main sections: the production section
108 and the surface section. The production section represents a one-dimensional model of a geothermal
109 well, used to estimate the fluid conditions at the wellhead. The surface section describes the
110 technologies applicable for geothermal energy conversion. This section includes two energy systems:
111 the Flash power plant and the Binary ORC power plant. Each technology is a simplified model, and
112 it is structured in modular blocks, which can be connected in series or in parallel, allowing for the
113 simulation of different plant configurations.

114 The classification of geothermal resources often relies on the Lindal diagram, which outlines the
115 temperature ranges suitable for various applications [Soelaiman, 2016; Gupta and Roy, 2007]. Each
116 thermodynamic block is selected based on a specific temperature classification, ensuring that the
117 energy system model aligns with the thermal characteristics of the geothermal resource, as showed in
118 Figure 1.

119
120 **Figure 1: Geothermal predictive model concept**

121 To develop an accurate and fast predictive model, meta-models have been designed. Meta-models
122 are mathematical tools that simplify the evaluation of input-output relationships in complex systems
123 [Palar et al., 2019]. To construct this meta-model, input parameter ranges were selected for each
124 thermodynamic block, showed in Supplementary Material A (SM.A). A homogeneous distribution
125 was created for each parameter, organized into three-dimensional square matrices. The resulting
126 matrix has dimensions of $n_p \times n_p \times n_p$. For each set of input matrix values, the three required parameters
127 were selected and evaluated in the simplified models, optimizing the installed power. The obtained
128 results were organized into output matrices and subsequently interpolated using linear
129 multidimensional interpolation [Chan et al., 1997] to generate the meta-model for all output
130 parameters. The value of dimensions of input matrix n_p is carefully chosen to create a dense input
131 grid as input and set to have a predictive error between the model and the metamodel of a maximum
132 of 0.5 %.

133 The following is a detailed description of each thermodynamic block, and the relative simplified
134 model.

135 2.2 Thermodynamic Blocks

136 2.2.1 Production section – Geothermal well

137 The first thermodynamic block represent the geothermal well. It describes the upward flow of
138 geothermal fluid from the deep reservoir to the surface, considering pressure losses and corresponding
139 temperature changes. It represents a simplified version of the Boiling Point Depth (BPD) Model [Di
140 Pippo, 2008; Grant et al., 2011], assuming one-dimensional, vertical, and adiabatic flow within the
141 well. Initial condition: The geothermal fluid starts as a subcooled liquid at the bottom of the well. As
142 the fluid rises, pressure decreases due to both gravity and dynamic flow effects. When the pressure
143 drops to the saturation pressure corresponding to the fluid's temperature, flashing occurs, part of the
144 liquid turns into vapor, and a two-phase flow begins. The depth at which flashing starts is called the
145 boiling depth (E.1). Depending on the relationship between L_f and the total well depth (L_{well}):

$$L_f = \frac{P_1 - P_{sat}(T_{geo})}{\rho g + C_2 m^2} \quad (E.1)$$

146 where P_1 is the pressure at the bottom of the well, P_{sat} is the saturation pressure, ρ is the fluid density,
147 g is the gravitational acceleration, and C_2 is a coefficient dependent on fluid properties and well
148 geometry.

- 149 • If $L_f \geq L_{well}$, the fluid reaches the surface as a liquid—natural flow occurs with minimal energy
150 loss.
- 151 • If $L_f < L_{well}$, the fluid rises in two-phase flow, which introduces additional pressure losses due
152 to hydrostatic pressure, friction, and phase slip (relative velocity between phases).

153 The SM.B shows and describes in more detail all the fundamental equations and parameters

154 2.2.2 Surface section – flash and binary power plant

155 The Flash system model is divided into two main blocks, representing the two fundamental phases of
156 the thermodynamic cycle in a geothermal power plant:

- 157 • *Steam production and separation:* This block covers the initial part of the cycle, from the
158 wellhead to the turbine. The geothermal fluid passes through an expansion valve and is then
159 separated into a vapor phase and a liquid phase. The separator regulates the pressure to ensure
160 the proper operation of the turbine. The amount of separated steam is managed to maximize
161 energy production without dropping below the minimum pressure required by the condenser.
162 Within the separator, pressure must remain between the pressure upstream of the valve and
163 the condenser pressure. To ensure this condition, a control parameter called x_{rel} is introduced
164 (E.2). It represents the ratio between the actual vapor fraction and the maximum allowable
165 vapor fraction. This parameter helps identify the operating conditions that maximize turbine
166 output without compromising system pressure balance.

$$x_{rel} = \frac{x_{sep}}{x_{max}} = \frac{x_{sep}}{x(h_1; P_{cond})} \quad (E.2)$$

- 167 • *Cooling and recirculation:* After passing through the turbine, the steam is condensed by a
168 cooling system consisting of a condenser, two pumps, and a cooling tower. Part of the
169 cooled water is reinjected into the system, while the remaining part is used as cooling fluid
170 in the condenser. The system ensures that operating temperatures remain within safe limits,
171 adapting to the external ambient air temperature.

172 A key feature of the model is its modular structure, which allows the output from the first block to
173 be used as input for additional thermodynamic cycles, such as in double flash systems.

174
175 The ORC binary thermodynamic block includes a heat exchanger (MHE), turbine, condenser, and
176 pump, with an additional fictitious separator used only for metamodel development. Unlike flash
177 systems, the ORC uses a secondary working fluid, allowing flexibility in fluid choice based on
178 thermodynamic and environmental performance. Selected fluids (R1233zd(E), R1234ze(Z),
179 isopentane) were chosen for their subcritical behavior and low Global Warming Potential (GWP).
180 The model determines optimal working fluid pressure and mass flow through an iterative process.
181 Heat exchange is governed by the geothermal temperature difference (ΔT_{geo}), adjusted to prevent
182 supercritical conditions. If the working fluid becomes superheated, it all enters the turbine; if not,
183 only the vapor portion does. The entire cycle is solved respecting mass and energy balances, ensuring
184 realistic sizing and compatibility with market-available heat exchangers.
185 The extended description and the equations of flash and binary blocks is reported in the SM.C.

186 2.3 Economic modeling

187 The economic evaluation of the system is carried out in two stages. The first stage involves
188 performing a cost analysis of the individual plant components, utilizing thermo-economic correlations
189 as those proposed in Turton (2008) [Turton, 2008]. Key parameters necessary for these correlations,
190 such as the surface area of the condenser and evaporator, the flow rates managed by the compressor,
191 and the volume of the separator, are derived from the thermodynamic blocks. For the separator, the
192 cost estimation employs the thermo-economic correlation provided by Mosaffa et al. (2017). The
193 specific components and the corresponding equations used for each are detailed in SM.D. Economic
194 estimations for geothermal wells typically rely on linear, exponential, or logarithmic correlations. In
195 this study, we adopted the correlation tailored for African applications as proposed by Shamoushaki
196 et al. (2021). The cost of the well can greatly affect the total cost of the plant, both in terms of initial
197 investment and LCOE [Shamoushaki et al., 2021, Karimi and Mansouri, 2018], and therefore special
198 attention is put on the number of well and their depth. The number of wells in the analysis depends
199 on the specific case. If known, it can be directly input into the economic model. Otherwise, two
200 options are available: assume one production and one reinjection well, or estimate the well count
201 using an empirical correlation based on plant capacity, as derived from literature data see equation
202 and reference in the SM.D.

203 With the economic model described above, the initial investment costs and total operation and
204 maintenance (O&M) costs are evaluated to determine the Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE). The
205 LCOE represents the full cycle costs (both fixed and variable) of a generation technology per unit of
206 energy, enabling comparisons across different technologies irrespective of their size, cost structure,
207 or lifespan [Ueckerdt et al., 2013]. In the context of renewable energy systems, the value of produced
208 energy is influenced by the resource availability and by the intermittent nature of the energy source.
209 Consequently, the LCOE is intrinsically linked to the variability patterns that define the energy
210 generation profile [Tran and Smith, 2018]. This parameter is particularly important in this study, as
211 it serves as a significant economic indicator [de Simon-Martin et al., 2022]. By consolidating these
212 costs into a single economic indicator, LCOE effectively quantifies the cost of electricity unitary
213 production cost (\$/kWh), as discussed by de Simón-Martín et al. (2022).

$$LCOE = \frac{C_{TCI} + C_{WD} + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{C_{pr}}{(1+r)^i}}{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{E_i}{(1+r)^i}} \quad (E.3)$$

214 The equation's parameters in E.3 are the following: C_{TCI} is the total capital investment cost; C_{pr} for
215 power plant is the Total Production Cost (C_{TPC}) [Shamoushaki et al., 2022] for other application is
216 the annual operating and maintenance cost ($C_{O\&M}$) [de Simon-Martin et al., 2022]; E_i is the annual
217 electricity produced; r is the discount rate; n is the lifetime of the energy system. For the calculation
218 of C_{TCI} , the method and parameters used in this work were taken from Karimi & Mansouri, (2018),
219 Shamoushaki et al., (2022). For the evaluation of LCOE with the integration of geothermal wells
220 Hackstein & Madlener (2021) have been adopted. While for the evaluation of C_{TPC} , Shamoushaki et
221 al. (2022) was followed. For $C_{O\&M}$, literature reference values were taken [Beckers et al., 2021]. The
222 discount rate was set for each application at 7% ([Beckers et al., 2021] and the lifetime varies between
223 power plant and other application is fixed to 30 years [Shamoushaki et al., 2021; Beckers et al., 2021;
224 Geoenvi 2023]. All correlations used and the general expression of the thermo-economic model are
225 shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Economic correlations for Thermo-economic model

Cost type	Relation
Total Cycle Cost	$TC_B = \sum_{i=1st\ component}^{i-th\ component} C_i$
Cost of site preparation	$C_{site} = 0.05 * TC_B$
Cost of service facilities	$C_{serv} = 0.05 * TC_B$
Allocated cost	$C_{alloc} = 0$
Total Direct Permanent Investment	$C_{DPI} = TC_B + C_{site} + C_{serv} + C_{alloc}$
Cost of contingencies and contractor's fee	$C_{cont} = 0.18 * C_{DPI}$
Total depreciable capital	$C_{TDC} = C_{DPI} + C_{cont}$
Cost of plant startup	$C_{startup} = 0.1 * C_{TDC}$
Permanent investment	$C_{TPI} = C_{TDC} + C_{startup}$
Working capital	$C_{WC} = 0$
Total Capital Investment	$C_{TCI} = C_{TPI} + C_{WC}$
Cost of wages and benefits	$C_{WB} = 0.035 * C_{TDC}$
Cost of salaries and benefits	$C_{SB} = 0.035 * C_{TDC}$
Cost of materials and services	$C_{TPI} = C_{WB}$
Cost of maintenance overhead	$C_{MO} = 0.05 * C_{WB}$
Direct Manufacturing costs	$C_{DMC} = C_{MO} + C_{TPI} + C_{SB} + C_{WB}$
Fixed Manufacturing Cost	$C_{FIX} = 0.02 * C_{TDC}$
Total annual cost of manufacture	$C_{COM} = C_{DMC} + C_{FIX}$
General Expense	$C_{GE} = 0$
Total production cost	$C_{pr} = C_{COM} + C_{GE}$

227

2.4 Case studies

2.4.1 Olkaria Geothermal Field

The case study to which the model developed in this work is applied in the Olkaria geothermal field, focusing on data from wells that feed steam to Olkaria IV. The power plant is a single flash with an installed capacity of 150 MW_e, and it has two turbines, each with a rated capacity of 75 MW_e. The net output capacity is 140 MW_e and exploits a liquid-dominated resource hosted in Trachyte formation between 1.2 to 3 km below the surface [Musonye, 2015]. The plant is served by 21 wells: 18 production wells and 3 re-injections wells. Each turbine is fed by a steam line with an intake flow rate of 135kg/s, 180°C temperature, and pressure between 9-12 bar. Several scenarios were analyzed, which are briefly described below and discussed in more detail in the following section:

- 1) Scenario Base case: This scenario represents the case study of Olkaria IV, thus using the data regarding the wells, a Single Flash system was calculated
- 2) Scenario Double Flash (FII): In this scenario, another flash is added to the results obtained for a single flash by connecting two thermodynamic blocks
- 3) Scenario Triple Flash (FIII): In this scenario, an additional thermodynamic block is added to the FII case to simulate a third level of power generation
- 4) Single Flash and Binary cycle (FI - ORC) scenario: here an ORC-type thermodynamic block is added to the basecase scenario
- 5) Double Flash and Binary cycle (FI - ORC) scenario: Here, however, a thermodynamic block is added to the FII scenario ORC

248 **2.4.2 Life Cycle Assessment**

249 Data collection was carried out to calculate the environmental impact of a sustainability analysis. The
250 approach followed was Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), per the framework established by ISO 14040
251 and ISO 14044. The objective is to determine the environmental impact of Olkaria and identify the
252 most significant environmental indicators and compare it to other systems. The approach used for this
253 analysis is cradle-to-gate type. The system boundaries encompass all processes related to the
254 construction, operation, and maintenance phases. The end-of-life phase is not considered due to the
255 lack of a disposal program. The functional unit selected is the electrical energy produced by the
256 powerplant in kWh, considering a useful 30-year lifetime and a capacity factor of 0.94, corresponding
257 to 8234 hours/year of operation.

258 **2.5 Environmental model**

259 The processes for the construction phase which were modeled in this settlement are the geothermal
260 wells and wellheads; the building hosting the powerplant, and the collection pipelines. The average
261 geothermal wells depth is 3000 m each. The collection pipelines are divided into 28 km of production
262 and 5 km of re-injection pipe. The machinery and power plant have not been modelled with primary
263 data from KenGen because of lack of data. Consequently, machinery and plant data were adopted
264 from the model proposed by Karlsdottir et al. (2015). For the scenario analysis involving the ORC
265 plant, the reference inventory for the machinery was taken from Frick et al., 2010.

266 The operation phase consumes 40.4 m³ of water per day for plant operation and approximately 126
267 MWh of electricity for heat distribution. Of this electricity, 16% is taken from the national grid and
268 84% from plant production. Direct emissions to the atmosphere are mainly CO₂, H₂S, H₂ and CH₄.
269 Six make-up wells are expected to be built in 25 years to maintain the geothermal steam flow rate at
270 the required level. In addition, lubricant oil is consumed for the machinery, while Sodium Carbonate
271 is used for anticorrosion and anti-scaling of the pipes. All inventory data are reported in
272 Supplementary Materials. The results shown in this paper refer to the single score. The contribution
273 analysis of the main indicator analyzed is reported in the SM.F.

274 **3 Results**

275 **3.1 Validation techno-economic**

276 **3.2 Results metamodels**

277 The thermodynamic model is validated by comparing several power plants analyzed in the literature,
278 and this is reported in the Supplementary Materials (SM.G). The general results of the metamodels
279 are reported in the following paragraph.

280 **3.2.1 Thermodynamic metamodels – Power Production**

281 Figure 2 compares three geothermal technologies, by analyzing installed power as a function of flow
282 rate and geothermal fluid temperature, with an external temperature fixed at 30°C. The meta-models
283 estimate power output, highlighting significant differences in operational temperature ranges. The
284 Single Flash system achieves high power output at geothermal temperatures above 250°C, where the
285 Binary ORC is ineffective. The Double Flash outperforms the Single Flash, particularly between
286 100°C and 150°C, increasing power by 6-7%, and above 200°C, where gains exceed 20%. However,
287 in high ambient temperatures, rising condensation temperatures reduce efficiency, limiting power
288 gains to 0.5-1%, making the system less viable.

289 Comparing Figure 2A and Figure 2B, the Double Flash expands the installed power area beyond 50
 290 MW and shows steeper power growth with increasing flow rate (m_{geo}) and geothermal temperature
 291 (T_{geo}). The Binary ORC, within its operational range, enables slightly larger plants than the flash
 292 systems at the same geothermal conditions. For example, at 200°C and 400 kg/s, the ORC reaches
 293 20.9 MW, Single Flash 20.1 MW, and Double Flash 23.6 MW. For lower flow rates (<200 kg/s) at
 294 maximum T_{geo} , installed capacities remain moderate: Single Flash (~37 MW), Double Flash (~46
 295 MW, +24%), ORC (~12 MW).

296 A key distinction lies in operational temperature ranges: ORC functions between 80-200°C, while
 297 flash systems extend from 100°C to >350°C, allowing greater energy exploitation at high
 298 temperatures. While power output is similar when operating at the same temperature, the flash
 299 systems leverage higher temperature resources for greater efficiency. Prediction uncertainty varies,
 300 being lowest for Single Flash, higher for ORC, and highest for Double Flash. These findings clarify
 301 each technology's capacity and optimal conditions based on flow rate and temperature parameters.
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305 **Figure 2: Metamodel surface representing the power installed for Single (A), Double Flash (B) and**
 306 **ORC Binary (C)**

307 3.2.2 Economic metamodels – Power Production

308 This section presents the results of the economic metamodels. Validating the model requires a similar
 309 approach to the thermodynamic model but with actual LCOE values for specific cases, which are
 310 rarely provided alongside necessary thermodynamic and economic parameters in literature. Thus, the
 311 model's predictions can only be compared to known reference values.

312 A major contributor to total plant cost and LCOE is the cost of wells, primarily influenced by their
 313 number and depth. To assess this impact, four scenarios with well depths of 1000 m, 2000 m, 3000
 314 m, and 4000 m were analyzed. Figure 3 illustrates the LCOE (c\$/kWh) as a function of geothermal
 315 resource flow rate (1-80 kg/s) and temperature, with reference values for photovoltaic (8.7 c\$/kWh,

316 yellow), wind (8.4 c\$/kWh, purple), and gas turbine (18 c\$/kWh, red) from Trinomics B.V. (2020).
 317 The maximum cost threshold is 30 c\$/kWh, beyond which the technology is not viable.
 318 For low flow rates and temperatures, the LCOE is high but decreases rapidly as conditions improve.
 319 However, increasing well depth shifts the low-LCOE area significantly to the right, reducing cost-
 320 effectiveness. Reference LCOE ranges from IEA (2023) and IRENA (2017) stand at 12-8.8 c\$/kWh
 321 and 14-4 c\$/kWh, respectively. Additionally, the analysis considers a maximum flow limit of 140
 322 kg/s, focusing on intermediate-sized plants (20-30 MW). Larger plants, capable of handling higher
 323 flow rates, remain cost-effective even at lower temperatures, particularly when flow rate and
 324 temperature increase significantly.

325

326

327 **Figure 3: Metamodel surface representing LCOE (c\$/kWh) for different scenarios well-depth.** Wells Depth
 328 (WD): A. 1000m; B. 2000m; C. 3000m; D. 4000m. (Red line = Gas Turbine; Yellow line=Photovoltaic ; Purple line =Wind)

329 3.3 Case studies: Olkaria IV

330 Figure 4 presents the tool's predictions for both energy and economic analyses in a comprehensive
 331 manner. In the energy analysis (Figure 4A), the red bar represents the original Olkaria IV plant data,
 332 which features a turbine rated at 150 MW and a net output of 140 MW. In comparison, the Basecase
 333 prediction calculates a net power of 137.9 MW, only 1.7% lower than the actual value, based on an
 334 evaluated liquid flow of approximately 721 kg/s at 179°C from the separator. Building on this, the "F
 335 II" scenario introduces a second flash turbine that adds 26 MW to yield a total output of 163.9 MW,
 336 utilizing a secondary flow of 626 kg/s at 111°C from a second separator. Further, the "F III" scenario
 337 contributes an additional 4.5 MW (total 168.4 MW), corresponding to installed capacity increases of
 338 16.9% for F II and 20.1% for F III relative to the Base case. When integrating an ORC system, the
 339 "F I – ORC" scenario—using the same input data as F II—achieves an increase of approximately
 340 29.2 MW (about 19.2%), while the "F II – ORC" scenario, which builds on the F II output, adds an
 341 extra 5.6 MW for a total increase of 20.89%. The economic analysis (Figure 4B) shows that the base

342 scenario is estimated at roughly \$517 million in total costs (CAPEX plus OPEX over a 30-year
 343 lifespan), with OPEX accounting for 31.3% and CAPEX for 68.7% of this value. The F II scenario
 344 incurs a cost increase of approximately 19.8% compared to the base case, and the F III scenario sees
 345 a 27.3% increase. Scenarios incorporating an ORC system generally lead to higher costs for a modest
 346 power gain of about 3 MW, with the “F I – ORC” and “F II – ORC” scenarios showing cost increases
 347 of 24.1% and 27.3%, respectively—findings that align with literature reports [Scarlat et al., 2020;
 348 IRENA, 2017; Sigfusson and Uihlein, 2015] attributing higher installation and maintenance expenses
 349 to binary ORC systems compared to flash systems. Notably, the LCOE, represented by the orange
 350 line and dots, exhibits minimal variation across the scenarios, increasing slightly from approximately
 351 4.01 c\$/kWh in the Basecase to 4.17 c\$/kWh in the most economically disadvantageous scenario.

352
 353 **Figure 4: Bar graph for installable power (left) and bar graph for economic cost (right) for different**
 354 **scenarios of Olkaria IV**

355 **3.3.1 Life Cycle Assessment**

356 The single score for the analyzed scenarios, evaluated using the European normalization and
 357 weighting set from the EF3.1 methodology. This assessment also incorporates renewable energy
 358 systems from the Ecoinvent 3.10 database—namely, wind (WIND), photovoltaic (PV), the Kenyan
 359 (KE) national mix, and an averaged EU mix (Mix EU) derived from national high-voltage electricity
 360 production data in countries such as Italy, Spain, France, and Germany. As shown in Figure 5, all
 361 geothermal scenarios exhibit a markedly lower environmental impact compared to the EU energy
 362 mix, with reductions exceeding 60%. In particular, when compared to the baseline case, the
 363 geothermal scenarios demonstrate significant improvements: the FI–ORC scenario achieves the
 364 greatest reduction at 15.9%, followed by reductions of 7.33% for F II, 2.08% for F III, and 9.95% for
 365 F II–ORC. These findings underscore the potential of geothermal exploitation technologies to
 366 enhance environmental performance and suggest that, relative to established renewable sources like
 367 wind and PV, geothermal systems offer a more sustainable alternative.

Figure 5: Single score comparison of all geothermal Scenarios and other energy sources

3.3.2 Sustainability analysis

Based on the results from the various analyses conducted, the information is integrated to determine the most sustainable scenario. Using the basecase as a reference, the relative percentage difference of each analysed indicator, considering of absolute values, is evaluated. For each parameter, a score ranging from 1 to 4 to the scenarios is assigned, where a lower score indicates poorer outcomes (characterized by smaller plant sizes, higher economic costs, or more significant environmental impacts). A higher score represents better outcomes (associated with larger plant sizes, reduced costs, and lower environmental impacts). Figure 6, on the left, presents the calculated values of relative difference (derived from absolute values) alongside the corresponding assigned scores, accompanied by a colour scale. Subsequently, potential preference approaches for selecting the scenarios are defined. Specifically, these approaches include an *Equal* approach that equally considers energy, economic, and environmental analyses, as well as three additional approaches (Energy, Economic, Environmental) that prioritize one of the three parameters. Table 2 outlines the weights assigned to each indicator. Finally, by multiplying the scores assigned to the scenarios by the weights of each approach, it is obtained a table displaying the total weighted score for each scenario. A lower score means a lesser level of sustainability, whereas a higher score corresponds to greater sustainability. The results indicate that the FI-ORC scenario emerges as the optimal solution for both the equitable and environmental approaches.

Regarding the energy approach, FI and FII-orc exhibit the same maximum score. Conversely, for the economic approach, scenario FII is identified as the best option, followed closely by FI-orc in the second position. In conclusion, scenario FIII is the least favourable among all the considered approaches. Therefore, it is asserted that the most sustainable solution for the Olkaria IV plant is integrating an ORC system alongside the existing single flash system.

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Table 2: Weighting Approach

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Equal</i>	<i>Energy</i>	<i>Environmental</i>	<i>Economic</i>
Energy [MW]	0.33	0.5	0.25	0.25
Economic [\$ or \$/kWh]	0.33	0.25	0.25	0.5
Environmental [Pt/kWh]	0.33	0.25	0.5	0.25

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397

398 **Figure 6: Score Matrix of relative difference and score level (on the left) and Decision-making results**
 399 **(On the right)**

400 4 Conclusion

401 A simplified model has been developed to assess the feasibility of geothermal resource utilization for
 402 electricity generation using minimal input parameters. The model is structured in a modular
 403 framework, based on metamodel approach, allowing for the evaluation of different technologies
 404 individually and their potential integration. The results obtained from the metamodels are the
 405 following:

- 406 • Double Flash technology demonstrates superior performance over Single Flash, particularly
 407 in the 100-150°C range and above 200°C, achieving power gains exceeding 20%.
- 408 • While Binary ORC operates effectively between 80-200°C and enables slightly larger plants
 409 under certain conditions, flash systems exploit higher temperature resources more efficiently,
 410 making them more suitable for high-temperature geothermal applications.
- 411 • Well depth significantly impacts total plant costs and LCOE, with deeper wells shifting cost-
 412 effective operation to higher flow rates and temperatures, reducing overall economic
 413 feasibility.
- 414 • While geothermal LCOE decreases with improved flow rate and temperature conditions,
 415 larger plants (20-30 MW) remain cost-effective even at lower temperatures, particularly when
 416 high flow rates are available.

417 The model is applied to a real case study, the Olkaria IV power plant case study. The analysis
418 integrates energy, economic, and environmental factors to determine the most sustainable scenario
419 for geothermal power plant optimization. A comparative evaluation is performed by assigning scores
420 to different scenarios based on relative percentage differences in key indicators. The results indicate
421 that the FI-ORC scenario consistently ranks as the most sustainable option under equal-weighted and
422 environmental approaches. Under the energy-focused approach, FI-ORC and FII-ORC achieve the
423 highest scores, while the economic approach favours the FII scenario, with FI-ORC as a close second.
424 Conversely, all evaluation criteria consistently identify the FIII scenario as the least favourable.
425 Ultimately, the findings highlight that the most sustainable solution is integrating an Organic Rankine
426 Cycle (ORC) system with the existing single flash system at the Olkaria IV plant. This approach
427 optimizes energy production while balancing economic and environmental considerations,
428 reinforcing the benefits of a hybrid geothermal system.

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433 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

434 Claudio Zuffi: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology,
435 Software, Validation, Visualisation, Writing- original Draft, Writing – Review and editing.

436 Daniele Fiaschi: Funding acquisition, Investigation, Supervision, Project administration, Resources,
437 Writing- review and editing

438 Xavier Musonye: Data curation, Resources, Supervision, Writing- review and editing

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440 Maryvelma Nafula: Supervision, Project administration

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